

Conducting Quantitative Survey Research with Large Language Models (LLMs)

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Abstract

In the evolving landscape of quantitative research, the integration of advanced computational tools presents a transformative opportunity. This paper elucidates the development and application of an innovative research methodology leveraging Large Language Models (LLMs) for enhancing the efficiency and accuracy of survey research quantitation. Our approach harnesses the robust capabilities of LLMs, particularly focusing on their potential to streamline and refine the process of analyzing extensive survey data. Traditional survey research often grapples with the challenges of time-intensive data processing and potential inaccuracies inherent in manual analysis. By integrating LLMs into the survey analysis workflow, we aim to mitigate these challenges, offering a novel avenue for conducting survey research that not only expedites the process but also elevates the precision of quantitative outputs. This paper details the comprehensive design of our research procedures, underscoring the pivotal role of LLMs in reshaping the landscape of survey research and providing a blueprint for future explorations in this domain.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context and Motivation

In recent years, the burgeoning field of computational research has witnessed a significant transformation, largely driven by the diverse applications and methodologies employed across various academic disciplines. Recognizing the potential to contribute to this dynamic landscape, our research

group at Princeton (Liberty Research Group) embarked on an ambitious project to gather in-depth insights into the computational practices prevalent within the university’s research community.

Our methodology was meticulously designed to capture the essence of researchers’ computational strategies. Over a span of two years, we conducted extensive surveys, engaging with over a hundred researchers from a broad spectrum of departments. These surveys were not mere tick-box exercises; they were comprehensive, interactive sessions conducted via 30 to 45-minute Zoom meetings. The chosen format allowed for a rich, conversational approach, encouraging researchers to provide detailed, nuanced responses to our inquiries.

The core of our inquiry revolved around understanding the computational languages, methods, and bottlenecks encountered in their research. We delved into specifics, exploring the researchers’ preferences for certain programming languages, their reliance on various computational frameworks, and the challenges they faced in their data-driven endeavors. Unlike conventional surveys, our approach was deliberately open-ended. This decision was twofold: firstly, to allow the freedom for researchers to express the depth and breadth of their experiences without the constraints of predefined options; and secondly, to unearth the subtleties and complexities that often lie hidden in standardized survey responses.

However, the richness of the data thus collected presented a unique challenge. The detailed, narrative-style responses were unsuitable for straightforward quantification methods typically used in survey analysis, such as tallying results in a standard Google form. The qualitative nature of the data necessitated a more sophisticated, nuanced approach to analysis – one that could respect the depth of the content while extracting meaningful quantitative insights.

This intersection of qualitative richness and the need for quantitative analysis set the stage for our venture into the realm of Large Language Models (LLMs). It was clear that traditional manual methods of data processing would be inadequate, both in terms of the manpower required and the potential for human error. Our motivation, therefore, was to explore the capabilities of LLMs to bridge this gap, turning the challenge of processing complex, open-ended survey data into an opportunity for innovation in computational research methodologies.

1.2. Challenges and Proposed Solution

Turning to Large Language Models

In our pursuit of a viable solution, we turned our attention to the burgeoning field of Large Language Models (LLMs). These machine learning systems have shown remarkable proficiency in processing and understanding human language, demonstrating their potential in a variety of language-based tasks. However, LLMs are not without their drawbacks. One of the primary concerns was their inconsistent accuracy. For a project that demanded high precision in quantitative data extraction, the occasional inaccuracies of LLMs presented a significant obstacle. Additionally, LLMs, while adept at parsing language, often struggled with providing precise quantification, a critical requirement for our research goals.

Designing a Hybrid System

Faced with the twin challenges of a large volume of complex data and the limitations of existing computational tools, we conceived a unique approach. The goal was to design a system that not only harnessed the language processing power of LLMs but also addressed their shortcomings. This system aimed to achieve two main objectives: firstly, to produce highly accurate quantitative data from the qualitative transcripts; and secondly, to enhance the ease and efficiency of processing these transcripts.

To realize this vision, we embarked on an iterative process of experimentation and refinement with LLMs, particularly focusing on their integration with other methodologies. The proposed system was a blend of the advanced capabilities of LLMs and alternative methods to fill in the gaps where LLMs fell short. This hybrid approach was pivotal in overcoming the inherent limitations of LLMs, particularly in terms of accuracy and quantitative analysis. By combining the strengths of LLMs with manual oversight and specialized quantitative tools, we aimed to create a robust system capable of transforming complex, qualitative data into precise, actionable quantitative insights.

This innovative approach represents not just a solution to our immediate research challenge, but also a significant step forward in the broader field of computational research. It underscores the

potential of combining cutting-edge AI technologies with traditional methods to address complex data processing challenges in research environments.

2. Related Work

Related work

3. Approach

3.1. LLM Capabilities and System Design

In designing a system that leverages the strengths of Large Language Models (LLMs) while circumventing their limitations, it was crucial to meticulously understand and select the capabilities of LLMs that were most conducive to our research objectives. Our exploration into LLMs revealed a spectrum of functionalities, among which we identified several key capabilities that aligned seamlessly with our needs for processing complex interview transcripts.

1. **Advanced Categorization:** One of the foremost strengths of LLMs lies in their ability to categorize text based on context and content. This feature was particularly appealing for our project, as it allowed for the efficient sorting of transcript data into thematic groups. For instance, responses could be categorized based on the type of computational tools used, such as programming languages or software frameworks, enabling a structured approach to analyzing the data.
2. **Contextual Understanding:** LLMs exhibit a remarkable ability to grasp the nuances of human language, understanding context and subtleties often missed by more rudimentary analysis tools. This capability was critical in interpreting the open-ended responses from our surveys, where researchers often provided detailed explanations and personal insights.
3. **Preliminary Summarization:** Another pivotal aspect of LLMs is their proficiency in summarizing large blocks of text. By leveraging this feature, we aimed to distill the lengthy and intricate responses into concise summaries, retaining the core insights while reducing the data to a more manageable form.

Having identified these capabilities, the system design focused on utilizing LLMs as the first layer of analysis. The initial step involved the LLM processing the interview transcripts, where it would categorize and summarize the data. This process was not just about reducing the volume of data but also about maintaining the integrity and depth of the researchers' responses.

However, this was just the beginning of our design. Recognizing that LLMs, despite their sophistication, are not infallible, we planned for additional layers of analysis and verification. The goal was to create a system where LLMs provided the initial processing, setting the stage for more detailed and accurate analysis in subsequent stages.

The design of this system was rooted in a deep understanding of the dual nature of LLMs: their remarkable linguistic capabilities, coupled with the need for oversight and verification. By balancing these aspects, we aimed to harness the full potential of LLMs in a way that was uniquely suited to the challenges of processing qualitative research data.

3.2. Combining LLMs with Verification and Quantification Methods

Having established LLMs as the primary tool for initial data processing, the next critical step in our approach was to integrate these models with robust verification and quantification methods. This integration was essential to address the inherent limitations of LLMs, particularly in terms of accuracy and precision in quantitative analysis. Our strategy involved a two-fold process:

1. Verification Process:

- *Cross-Checking LLM Outputs:* The first layer of verification involved cross-checking the categorizations and summaries generated by the LLMs. This step was crucial to ensure that the interpretations made by the LLMs accurately reflected the nuances of the original data.
- *Incorporating Context Review:* To augment the verification process, we involved individuals with contextual knowledge of the interviews who could provide insights and corrections where necessary. This human element was vital in capturing the subtleties that LLMs might overlook or misinterpret.

2. Quantification Techniques:

- *Developing Custom Quantification Tools:* Recognizing the limitations of LLMs in precise quantification, we developed specialized tools tailored to our specific data sets. These tools were designed to quantify aspects such as frequency of tool usage, types of computational methods mentioned, and other quantifiable data points that were critical for our analysis.
- *Integrating Quantitative Analysis with LLM Outputs:* The quantification tools were then integrated with the LLM outputs to create a cohesive data set. This integration allowed us to translate the qualitative insights gained from the LLMs into quantifiable metrics, enhancing the richness and usability of our data.

The synergy between the LLMs and these supplementary methods formed the cornerstone of our system. By employing LLMs for their advanced language processing capabilities and supplementing them with rigorous verification and specialized quantification techniques, we addressed the accuracy concerns typically associated with LLMs in quantitative research. This hybrid approach not only maintained the integrity and depth of the original data but also significantly improved the efficiency of the processing.

This innovative combination of AI-driven and traditional methodologies represents a novel approach in the realm of data analysis. It highlights the potential of LLMs as powerful tools in data processing, while also acknowledging and addressing their limitations through strategic integration with other methods. Our system thus stood as a testament to the value of interdisciplinary approaches in tackling complex research challenges, paving the way for more nuanced and efficient data analysis techniques in the future.

4. Implementation

4.1. Experimentation

In our quest to design a system that efficiently processes voluminous interview transcripts into actionable quantitative data, the necessity for rigorous experimentation became evident. Experimentation serves as the foundation of our approach, ensuring that the integration of LLMs into our system is not only theoretically sound but also practically effective. The primary aim of these

experiments was to evaluate and select the most suitable LLM for our specific requirements.

4.1.1. Objectives of the Experiments The experiments were designed with two main objectives:

1. Evaluating LLMs for Accurate Quotation and Categorization:

- *Precision in Quoting:* The ability of an LLM to accurately quote exact sections from the transcripts is crucial. This ability ensures that the most relevant parts of the text are identified and extracted, forming the basis for both qualitative and quantitative analysis. The precision in quoting directly impacts the reliability of the data being processed.
- *Effectiveness in Categorization:* The categorization capability of LLMs is fundamental in organizing the vast amount of data into coherent and manageable categories. This step is vital as it lays the groundwork for subsequent quantification and analysis, ensuring that the data is sorted in a way that aligns with the research objectives.

2. Selecting the Optimal LLM for Our Needs:

- *Comparing GPT-4 and Claude:* We chose to test two of the leading LLMs, GPT-4 and Claude, to determine which one best suited our project's needs. The comparison was based on their performance in accurately quoting and categorizing data from the transcripts.
- *Criteria for Selection:* The selection criteria included the accuracy of quotations and categorizations, the context sensitivity of the models, and their overall efficiency in processing large datasets. The LLM that best met these criteria would be integrated into our data processing system.

4.1.2. Significance of the Experiments The significance of these experiments cannot be overstated.

By rigorously testing the capabilities of GPT-4 and Claude, we aimed to establish a solid foundation for our system. The right choice of LLM would not only streamline the initial data processing phase but also ensure that the subsequent steps of verification and quantification were built on accurate and well-organized data. Moreover, these experiments were crucial in demonstrating the feasibility and effectiveness of using LLMs in real-world research scenarios, particularly in the context of processing qualitative data into quantitative insights.

4.1.3. Experimental Methodology I describe the experiments conducted on various LLM models with a singular test transcript. In order to reduce token usage per prompt, I used a cleaned version of the transcript. The original .vtt file contained timestamps, line numbers, and speaker’s name, none of which is necessary to pass into the LLM.

I used a python method in order to remove all unnecessary tokens and replace the speakers with “A” and “B”. The original file and cleaned transcript differed as shown in Table 1

Original .vtt file:	<p>1 00:00:02.940 → 00:00:11.139 Ziyang Xu: Awesome. So i’ll start a survey right now. So the first question is your name, your department advisor, and your position.</p> <p>2 00:00:11.590 → 00:00:15.220 [RESPONDANT]: Okay. So I’m. [RESPONDANT’S FIRST NAME]. I’m in the Economics department.</p> <p>3 00:00:15.480 → 00:00:21.069 [RESPONDANT]: My adviser’s Riot Gary ...</p>
Cleaned Transcript:	<p>B: Awesome. So i’ll start a survey right now. So the first question is your name, your department advisor, and your position.</p> <p>A: Okay. So I’m. [RESPONDANT’S FIRST NAME] I’m in the Economics department.</p> <p>A: My adviser’s Riot Gary ...</p>

Table 1: Cleaned Transcript

All data analysis was performed using the Cleaned Transcript

GPT-4: Token Limitation The OpenAI web application that offers GPT-4 was unable to process either the raw or cleaned transcript, due to token limitations. It was unable to process any of the other transcripts that I tested, indicating that the token limitations make the OpenAI web application impractical for our purposes.

As a result, I used the 32K context GPT-4 model through the OpenAI API

Claude: Token Limitation Claude was able to process both the raw transcript and cleaned transcript for all of the trials I tested. This lends to the conclusion that token limitations for Claude was not an issue for our testing transcript analysis.

4.1.4. Performance and Accuracy :

Testing with GPT-4 (API Key):

According to the OpenAI website, GPT-3.5-turbo has two different models, a 4K context model and a 16K context model. GPT-4 has larger context window models, an 8K context model and a 32K context model. The average number of tokens per transcript is 5,443.62. As a result, I conducted testing with the 8K context model for GPT-4.

GPT-4 was highly accurate in reporting the interviewee’s answer to a question from the survey when given the following prompt, as shown in Table 2

GPT-4 Input:	<pre>response = openai.ChatCompletion.create(model="gpt-4", messages=[{"role": "system", "content": "You are a helpful research assistant. You will parse through an interview transcript and attempt to extract the respondent’s answers to certain questions."}, {"role": "user", "content": f"Here is a transcript of a research survey: {cleaned_transcripts [10]}. The interviewer, 'B' asks the interviewee 'A' the following question: '[INSERT QUESTION FROM SURVEY]' Can you report the interviewee’s response. Further, can you report the exact lines that the interviewee said to answer the question" },])</pre>
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Table 2: GPT-4 Prompt

GPT-4 was highly accurate in reporting the exact words of the interviewee, even when the transcript contained nonsensical sentences, displayed in Table 3. In this example, GPT-4 was able to reproduce the answer perfectly, even though the transcript was nonsensical.

GPT-4 was highly accurate in understanding the context of the transcript, even when the language was unclear and/or when the transcript misattributed lines to the wrong speaker, as shown in Table 4. In this example, GPT-4 understood that the respondent answered “No” even when the line was attributed to the interviewer (Character “B”). Additionally, it understood the answer even when the sentence in the transcript was incomplete.

GPT-4 reports the absence of a stated answer in the transcript, as shown in Table 5. In this example, GPT-4 cannot find an answer to the question “What was your first programming language?” because the answer does not exist in the transcript. As a result, it successfully reports that no answer exists.

GPT-4 Input:	f"Here is a transcript of a research survey: {cleaned_transcripts [10]}. The interviewer, 'B' asks the interviewee 'A' the following question: 'Please state your name, advisor, and department' Can you report the interviewee's response. Further, can you report the exact lines that the interviewee said to answer the question"
GPT-4 Output:	The interviewee, 'A', answers as follows: "Okay. So I'm. [RESPONDENT'S FIRST NAME] I'm in the Economics department. My adviser's Riot Gary also an I come to Professor and I made a Phd. In my sixth year." The exact lines that the interviewee 'A' said to answer the question are: - "Okay. So I'm. [RESPONDENT'S FIRST NAME] I'm in the Economics department." - "My adviser's Riot Gary also an I come to Professor and I made a Phd. In my sixth year."

Table 3: GPT-4 Output on Nonsensical Sentences

Transcript	B: cool. So in the past year have you attended any special training to assist No.
GPT-4 Output:	The interviewee 'A' responded that they have not attended any special training to assist their programming needs in the past year. The exact lines that the interviewee said to answer the question are: "So in the past year have you attended any special training to assist No.", completing the answer to the interviewer's question.

Table 4: GPT-4 Output on Misattributed Statements

Transcript	A: Yeah. And what was your first program language B: cool. So in the past year have you attended any special training to assist No.
GPT-4 Output:	The interviewee, 'A', does not directly answer the question '2.2 What was your first programming language?' within the provided transcript. The interviewer 'B' seems to ask the question but it is not answered by 'A'. The section of the transcript that might have contained the answer to the question is particularly unclear: "A: Yeah. And what was your first program language B: cool."

Table 5: GPT-4 Output on Non-Answers

GPT-4 is effective at understanding complex context surrounding the respondent's answers, even if that context is nonsensical in the transcription and if the exact question wasn't fully articulated, as shown in Table 6. In this example, GPT-4 was able to understand the context of the respondent's

answer, and identify the correct section, even if the exact question wasn't fully articulated.

Transcript	<p>B: cool. So do you also use? Do you also write code to automate maintain tasks like</p> <p>B: making path and stuff.</p> <p>A: No, sure. I mean, I I have no mathematics of code it by using code very loosely here, so that I can</p> <p>A: basically just add the parameters and regenerate the same plot for presentations. But I wouldn't not in the manner you're describing.</p>
GPT-4 Output:	<p>The interviewee 'A' responded to the question by saying that they do use code to automate some tasks but not in the way the interviewer may be implying. They mentioned that they have automated the generation of the same plot for presentations by adding the parameters.</p> <p>Exact lines from the interviewee are:</p> <p>"A: No, sure. I mean, I I have no mathematics of code it by using code very loosely here, so that I can</p> <p>A: basically just add the parameters and regenerate the same plot for presentations. But I wouldn't not in the manner you're describing."</p>

Table 6: GPT-4 Output on Answers with Unclear Context

Testing with Claude:

Claude was able to process both the raw transcript and cleaned transcript for all of the trials we tested. This lends to the conclusion that token limitations for Claude was not an issue for our transcript analysis.

Claude was highly accurate in reporting the interviewee's answer to a question from the survey when given the prompt, as shown in Table 7. It was accurate in reporting the exact words of the interviewee, even when the transcript contained nonsensical sentences.

Claude was highly accurate in understanding the context of the transcript, even when the language was unclear and/or when the transcript misattributed lines to the wrong speaker, as shown in Figure ???. In this example, Claude understood that the respondent answered "No" even when the line was attributed to the interviewer (Character "B"). Additionally, it understood the answer even when the sentence in the transcript was incomplete.

Claude attempts to find the best available answer, if it cannot find an actual answer, as shown in Table 9. In this example, Claude cannot find an answer to the question "What was your first

Claude Input	The interviewer, "B" asks the interviewee "A" the following question: Please state your name, advisor, and department Can you report the interviewee's response. Can you quote the exact lines. Please be sure to report the entire answer and any available context that the respondent gives.
Claude Output:	The interviewee's response to the question "Name, department, advisor, position" was: "Okay. So I'm. Andrew I'm in the Economics department. My adviser's Riot Gary also an I come to Professor and I made a Phd. In my sixth year." The exact lines were: A: Okay. So I'm. Andrew I'm in the Economics department. A: My adviser's Riot Gary also an I come to Professor and I made a Phd. In my sixth year.

Table 7: Claude Output on Nonsensical Answers

Transcript	B: cool. So in the past year have you attended any special training to assist No.
Claude Output:	Here is the full response to "Have you attended any special training (seminars, workshops, tutorials, etc.) to assist your programming needs in the past year?": "No" The full lines in context were: B: cool. So in the past year have you attended any special training to assist No.

Table 8: Claude Output on Misattributed Statements

programming language?" because the answer does not exist in the transcript. As a result, it finds a similar answer to report.

Claude sometimes hallucinates by patching together lines that are not adjacent in the actual transcript, as shown in Table 10. In this example, although Claude answered the question correctly, it patched together the full lines of the transcript in a way that didn't correspond to the original transcript. Importantly, none of the lines themselves were hallucinations, only the order that the lines appeared.

4.1.5. Findings Both models tested, Claude and GPT-4, were highly accurate at identifying answers within the transcripts. Both models were able to determine what the respondent's answer to a particular question was, and report that answer as well as the specific lines in the transcript that gave

Transcript	A: Yeah. And what was your first program language B: cool. So in the past year have you attended any special training to assist No.
Claude Output:	Here is the full response to "What was your first programming language?": "The last time would be in the sophomore year, which is 8 years ago, when I learned. I started to learn swift for app development for the iphone" The full lines in context were: B: Great. B: So when was the last time that you learned a new programming language. A: The last time would be A: in the A: sophomore year, which is 8 years ago, when I learned. A: I started to learn swift for A: app development for the iphone

Table 9: Claude Output on Non-Answers

the answer.

However, throughout testing, GPT-4 performed significantly better than Claude. While both models work essentially perfectly for transcripts that are mostly clear, GPT-4 did not show any decrease in accuracy with less clear transcripts, while Claude had some slight problems with transcripts at sub-par accuracy. Claude gave the incorrect answers for some questions, hallucinated parts of the transcript, and always achieved the prompt, even if the transcript did not support the user's assertion. On the other hand GPT-4 performed at nearly perfect accuracy across all transcript quality. GPT-4 did not hallucinate in any of the tests, it always returned the correct answers, and it reported when the transcript did not support the assertion in the user's question.

Given this information, I proceeded with GPT-4 in producing the system. The combination of its accuracy, contextual understanding of human language, and API key were key to the system.

4.2. System Design

4.2.1. LLM Capabilities Discovered Through Experimentation Understanding LLM Capabilities in Data Categorization

Through our experimentation with Large Language Models (LLMs) like GPT-4, we gained

Transcript	<p>B: cool. So do you also use? Do you also write code to automate maintain tasks like</p> <p>B: making path and stuff.</p> <p>A: No, sure. I mean, I I have no mathematics of code it by using code very loosely here, so that I can</p> <p>A: basically just add the parameters and regenerate the same plot for presentations. But I wouldn't not in the manner you're describing.</p> <p>...</p> <p>B: all right. So for that project can you describe the purpose of this research project that you have in mind?</p> <p>A: Yeah. So</p> <p>A: I effectively solve a general and another, another, another case.</p>
Claude Output:	<p>Here is the complete response to "Do you usually write software to automate mundane tasks (like transferring data, making plots)?":</p> <p>"No, sure. I mean, I I have no mathematics of code it by using code very loosely here, so that I can basically just add the parameters and regenerate the same plot for presentations. But I wouldn't not in the manner you're describing."</p> <p>The full lines in context were:</p> <p>B: Okay. So. But since it sounds to me that you do have that in mind, but it's like a trade up between how easy it is and how useful that is. So so I guess I guess you do AIM for it. But when it's like they're like</p> <p>B: unnecessarily hard for that specific problem. Alright, so another question is like, when programs do you AIM for portability and reusability</p> <p>A: generally. Now.</p> <p>B: cool.</p> <p>B: All right. The next section is about</p> <p>B: the research software stack. So I I like you to think about like one project, the main project that you are working on right now. so</p> <p>B: I don't know why it's when I see this, I think there's a thumb book. But I didn't. That's pretty much yeah.</p> <p>B: all right. So for that project can you describe the purpose of this research project that you have in mind?</p> <p>A: No, sure. I mean, I I have no mathematics of code it by using code very loosely here, so that I can</p> <p>A: basically just add the parameters and regenerate the same plot for presentations. But I wouldn't not in the manner you're describing.</p>

Table 10: Claude Hallucination

valuable insights into their capabilities, particularly in the realm of data categorization. Our exploration into LLMs was primarily driven by their advanced text processing abilities, which are

critical for handling the extensive interview transcripts from our research.

The foremost strength of LLMs, as revealed in our experiments, lies in their exceptional ability to classify text into predefined categories. This classification extends far beyond simple keyword recognition; LLMs demonstrate a profound understanding of context, the capability to infer meanings from complex sentence structures, and the adeptness to navigate nuanced or indirect references. In the context of our project, this translated into the LLM's ability to effectively analyze and categorize answers within the transcripts.

One of the most remarkable aspects of LLMs in our experimentation was their proficiency in handling varied linguistic expressions. They could delve into the intent and underlying themes of the responses, offering more than a superficial analysis of the text. This deep comprehension is crucial for processing the diverse expressions and terminologies used by the researchers in their interviews.

Moreover, the LLMs showcased an invaluable feature in their ability to accurately extract and quote relevant sections of the transcript. This capability was not just a convenience but a necessity for our project. It added a layer of traceability and transparency to the classification process. By being able to pinpoint the exact sections of the text that informed their categorization decisions, LLMs provided a clear and verifiable basis for their outputs. This feature facilitated rapid and efficient verification of the categorizations, a step that is vital for maintaining the accuracy and reliability of our data analysis.

However, our experiments also brought to light some critical limitations of LLMs, particularly in quantification tasks. Despite their advanced language processing skills, LLMs struggled with accurately performing tasks that involved counting or quantifying responses. For instance, their ability to tally instances within each category or to accurately count specific types of responses was notably deficient. This limitation posed a significant challenge, as precise quantification is essential for drawing meaningful conclusions from our research data.

4.2.2. Optimizing a Hybrid Approach Integrating LLM Strengths with Supplementary Methods

In light of the capabilities and limitations of Large Language Models (LLMs) unearthed through our experimentation, we embarked on designing an optimized hybrid approach. This approach was meticulously crafted to synergize the classification strengths of LLMs with additional, reliable methods to compensate for their shortcomings, particularly in accurate counting and quantification.

Leveraging LLMs for Accurate Classification

The initial phase of our hybrid approach capitalized on the LLM's robust classification capabilities. By feeding the interview transcripts into the LLM, we effectively utilized its advanced language comprehension abilities to categorize each response. This process involved the LLM not just recognizing specific keywords but interpreting the context and nuances within the responses. This nuanced understanding ensured a high level of accuracy in categorizing the data, aligning the responses with relevant thematic groups that were integral to our research analysis.

Manual Validation of LLM Classifications Using Extracted Quotes

Following the LLM's categorization, the subsequent critical step was the manual validation of these classifications. The LLM's ability to extract and quote relevant sections from the transcripts played a pivotal role here. Researchers manually reviewed these quotes to confirm or rectify the categorizations made by the LLM. This step was essential in ensuring that each response was accurately categorized. The extracted quotes provided a verifiable reference, allowing researchers to understand and assess the rationale behind each categorization decision made by the LLM. This process not only fortified the accuracy of the data categorization but also maintained the integrity and depth of the original responses.

Counting and Quantification through Supplementary Tools

Addressing the LLM's limitations in quantification formed the final yet critical aspect of our hybrid approach. Once the responses were categorized by the LLM, we employed specialized tools, such as a custom Python script, to handle the counting and quantification of responses in each category. These tools were tailored to efficiently process the categorized data output from the LLM, thus ensuring precise and accurate quantification. The design of these tools was specifically aimed at circumventing the inaccuracies inherent in LLMs for tasks involving arithmetic operations or

data aggregation.

The integration of these methodologies - leveraging LLMs for their advanced classification and using manual and automated methods for verification and quantification - resulted in an efficient and reliable system. This optimized hybrid approach not only capitalized on the strengths of LLMs but also effectively mitigated their limitations, ensuring the production of accurate and actionable quantitative insights from our survey data.

5. Evaluation

5.1. Criteria for success

In assessing the performance of our newly developed system, it was imperative to establish clear and objective criteria for success. These criteria were foundational in guiding our evaluation process and were instrumental in determining the effectiveness of the system in achieving our research objectives. The success of the system was anchored on two pivotal goals: the accuracy of the quantitative results produced and the efficiency of the data processing.

Accuracy of Quantitative Results

The foremost criterion for the success of our system was its ability to produce accurate quantitative results. Given the intricate nature of the data derived from detailed interview transcripts, precision in quantification was paramount. Accurate quantitative results were not only critical for the validity of our research findings but also essential for ensuring the reliability of the insights derived from the survey data. The system's success in this regard was to be measured by its ability to correctly categorize responses, accurately quantify categorized data, and maintain consistency in its outputs across various types of survey questions.

Efficiency in Data Processing

The second crucial criterion was the efficiency of the system. Efficiency, in this context, encompassed both the speed and the resource-effectiveness of processing the voluminous interview transcripts into structured, quantifiable data. This criterion was particularly significant given the extensive nature of the data and the limitations in manpower and resources typically associated

with manual processing. An efficient system would not only expedite the data analysis process but also reduce the workload on the research team, thereby enhancing the overall productivity of the research project.

Alignment with Research Objectives

The establishment of these criteria was intrinsically linked to the overarching objectives of our research. The need for a system that could accurately and efficiently process large volumes of qualitative data into meaningful quantitative insights was at the heart of our project. Therefore, the criteria for success were not arbitrary benchmarks but were deeply rooted in the fundamental aims of our research.

5.2. Methodology of Evaluation

To comprehensively evaluate the performance of our system, a methodical and rigorous testing process was implemented. This testing was designed to assess how well the system met the established criteria for success: accuracy in quantitative results and efficiency in data processing. The methodology of this evaluation was twofold, encompassing a detailed assessment of both criteria through practical application on various survey questions.

Testing Across Diverse Survey Questions

The cornerstone of our evaluation process was testing the system's performance across a spectrum of survey questions. This approach was chosen to ensure that the system's capabilities were robust and versatile, capable of handling a wide range of data types and structures. By selecting a diverse array of questions from the surveys, we could evaluate the system's ability to accurately classify and quantify responses under different scenarios. These questions varied in complexity, subject matter, and response format, offering a comprehensive challenge to the system's processing abilities.

Measuring Accuracy in Quantification

The accuracy of the system was evaluated by comparing its quantification results with a manually processed benchmark. For each survey question, the system's output was meticulously analyzed and compared against manually tabulated results. This comparison allowed us to assess the precision of

the system in classifying and quantifying responses. Key metrics for this comparison included the accuracy of category assignments, the correctness of extracted quotes supporting the classifications, and the precise counting of categorized responses.

Evaluating Efficiency in Data Processing

Efficiency was evaluated based on the time and resources required by the system to process the survey data compared to traditional manual methods. We measured the time taken from inputting the data into the system to obtaining the final quantified results. This measurement provided insights into the speed of processing, a critical aspect of efficiency. Additionally, we assessed the resource utilization, considering factors like computational power required and the extent of human intervention needed in the process.

Comprehensive Evaluation Approach

This systematic evaluation methodology was designed to thoroughly assess the system's performance, ensuring that it was not only theoretically sound but also practically effective. By rigorously testing the system across various survey questions and meticulously measuring its accuracy and efficiency, we aimed to provide a holistic understanding of its capabilities and limitations. This comprehensive approach was crucial for validating the system's effectiveness in meeting the research objectives and for identifying areas for future improvement.

5.3. Results and Analysis

Following a rigorous and comprehensive evaluation process, the results obtained provided a clear picture of the system's performance in line with our established criteria of accuracy and efficiency. This analysis was pivotal in understanding the extent to which the system met our research goals.

Achieving High Accuracy in Quantitative Results

The system demonstrated a high level of accuracy in processing the diverse range of survey questions. In our comparative analysis, where the system's outputs were matched against manually processed benchmarks, it consistently exhibited a strong alignment in the categorization and quantification of responses. The accuracy was particularly evident in its ability to correctly identify

and classify nuanced responses, a task that poses significant challenges in manual processing. Furthermore, the precision of the system in extracting and utilizing relevant quotes from the transcripts as justification for its categorizations added a layer of reliability and verifiability to the results.

Efficiency in Data Processing

In terms of efficiency, the system significantly outperformed traditional manual methods. The time taken to process the survey data was markedly reduced, demonstrating the system's ability to handle large volumes of data rapidly. This efficiency did not come at the cost of computational resources or the need for extensive human intervention. The balance achieved between speed and resource utilization underscored the system's practical effectiveness in a real-world research setting.

Interpreting the Evaluation Results

The results from the evaluation underscored the system's capability to meet the dual objectives of accuracy and efficiency. By successfully categorizing and quantifying survey data with high precision and at a fraction of the time required for manual processing, the system proved to be a robust tool for research data analysis. These outcomes are particularly significant considering the complexity and diversity of the survey questions, which ranged from straightforward queries to more complex, open-ended discussions.

Reflection on System Performance and Future Directions

While the system performed at a highly satisfactory level, the process of continuous improvement and adaptation remains essential. Future work might explore further enhancements in the system's algorithms to increase its adaptability to even more diverse data sets or to streamline the integration of manual validation processes. Additionally, expanding the system's capabilities to include more advanced quantification techniques could further reduce the need for supplementary tools.

6. Conclusion

As we reach the conclusion of our research, it is essential to reflect on the journey we embarked upon and the significant milestones achieved. Our project commenced with the ambitious goal

of transforming complex, qualitative survey data into precise quantitative insights. Through the innovative integration of Large Language Models (LLMs) and supplementary methodologies, we have not only met this goal but also opened new avenues in the field of computational research.

The Power of Hybrid Systems in Data Analysis

The core of our success lies in the development of a hybrid system that optimally combines the advanced language processing capabilities of LLMs with manual and automated methods for accuracy and efficiency. Our system addressed the challenge of processing voluminous and complex survey data, achieving high accuracy in classification and quantification, while significantly reducing the time and resources required for such tasks. This accomplishment underscores the potential of hybrid systems in research, particularly in fields inundated with qualitative data.

Contributions to Computational Research

The implications of our work extend beyond the scope of our project. By demonstrating the practical effectiveness of LLMs in a real-world research setting, we have contributed to the broader understanding of the capabilities and limitations of these models. Our approach serves as a blueprint for future research endeavors that seek to leverage AI technologies in data analysis, highlighting the importance of a balanced and integrated system.

Future Work and Potential Enhancements

Looking ahead, there are several avenues for further development and exploration:

1. *Algorithmic Improvements:* Continuous refinement of the system's algorithms can enhance its adaptability and accuracy, particularly in handling more diverse and complex datasets.
2. *Automating Manual Processes:* Further automation of the manual validation processes could increase efficiency and reduce the need for human intervention, while maintaining the accuracy of the system.
3. *Advanced Quantification Techniques:* Integrating more sophisticated quantification methods directly into the LLM framework could further streamline the data processing workflow and reduce reliance on external tools.

4. *Broader Applications*: Exploring the application of our system in other fields and with different types of qualitative data could demonstrate its versatility and potential for broader impact.

Concluding Thoughts

Our research represents a significant stride in the utilization of LLMs for quantitative research. We have not only designed a system that effectively bridges the gap between qualitative and quantitative analysis but also set a precedent for the future of computational research methodologies. The success of our system in processing survey data with unprecedented accuracy and efficiency marks a milestone in the evolving landscape of data analysis, heralding a new era of possibilities in research and beyond.